

Antiviral properties of polylactic acid and nano-TiO₂ for 3D printing

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ABSTRACT

Throughout history, viruses have consistently adapted to survive and spread. Understanding airborne transmission and surface survival emphasizes the necessity for antiviral materials. This study demonstrates virucidal reduction of human *Coronavirus 229E* and *Feline Calicivirus* on a polylactic acid and titanium dioxide nanoparticle composite with photocatalytic activity and UV activation. Mechanical properties and UV spectroscopy are also examined, suggesting the potential of the composite in medical and food applications through additive manufacturing.

1. Introduction

Throughout history, viral diseases have persisted, presenting diverse transmission mechanisms, genetic varieties, and susceptible hosts. Viruses adapt to changing environments, heightening the risk of contagion among animals and humans [1,2]. Identifying transmission routes is crucial; airborne transmission is a potentially infectious medium, influenced by variables like time and distance of propagation, material surfaces, especially plastic, have gained attention, as viruses like SARS-CoV-2 can survive on them for up to 72 h [3].

The incorporation of antiviral agents into polymeric matrices reduces virus transmission on surfaces. Several studies have investigated various agents, including ions metallic, nanomaterials, and natural compounds, to develop materials with virucidal capacity [4–6]. In this context, polymeric composites based on Poly(Lactic Acid) (PLA) are a promising alternative for the advancement of materials engineering [7,8], previous studies support their mechanical, thermal, durability and antibacterial properties [9].

In photocatalytic processes, titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanoparticles serve a role in the inactivation of viruses such as *influenza (H3N2)* [10], bacteriophage *MS2* [11], *SARS-CoV-2* [12] and *Bovine Coronavirus BCoV* [13]. The reduction of viral load primarily occurs through physical damage and chemical oxidation by reactive oxygen species (ROS), which interact with proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids, causing their degradation and deactivation.

3D printing emerges as a critical alternative due to disruptions in

traditional manufacturing methods and supply chains during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, printing personal protective equipment and medical devices [14].

The present research proposes to evaluate the antiviral activity of polylactic acid and TiO₂ nanoparticles composites in additive manufacturing, unprecedented in fused deposition modeling (FDM). This solution is promising for additive manufacturing and public health, offering long-lasting and effective protection against enveloped and non-enveloped viruses, applicable to plastic surfaces.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Polylactic acid (PLA) obtained from Ingeo (Ingeo TM Bioplástico, EE.UU.) and dioxide titanium (TiO₂) nanoparticles were sourced from (Sigma-Aldrich, Alemania). The viruses studied were *Human Coronavirus 229E* and *Feline Calicivirus*. The compounds were manufactured under industrial conditions [15], through melt blending of PLA and TiO₂ at 8 % by weight.

2.2. Characterization

The antiviral activity of the compounds was assessed on surfaces according to ISO 18061 and calculated [16]. Treated (T) PLA/TiO₂ and untreated (NT) specimens were printed (50 ± 1 x 50 ± 1 x 4 ± 0.2 mm).

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UV exposure used a BLB fluorescent lamp (350–400 nm, 0.25 mW/cm², 4 h). Antiviral activity was assessed using TCID₅₀. Lethality percentage against viruses was determined by Formula 1:

$$\text{Case fatality rate} = (1 - 10^{-\Delta V}) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where, ΔV is antiviral activity of photocatalyst with UV irradiation.

UV spectroscopy was used to assess transmittance in the range of 175 to 900 nm for both the filler and the polymeric compound, employing a Cary 4000 spectrophotometer. Photon energy was calculated using Formula 2:

$$E = 1240/\lambda \quad (2)$$

where E is the photon energy in electronvolts (eV), λ is the wavelength of electromagnetic radiation in nanometers (nm) and the constant 1240 is derived from unit conversion, considering the relationship between wavelength in nm and energy in eV.

Mechanical properties under tension and flexion were determined in each printing orientation: horizontal, vertical, and edge at a speed of 1 mm/s. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed for each fracture, a Carl Zeiss MERLIN microscope with secondary electron image resolution was used.

3. Results and discussion

Virus titers were assessed using the TCID₅₀ method for PLA and PLA/TiO₂ specimens under various conditions. Results in Table 1 show that the PLA/TiO₂ composite, exposed to *Feline Calicivirus* and UV radiation, demonstrated a viricidal activity after UV irradiation (V_L) value of 0.86, antiviral activity of photocatalyst with UV irradiation (ΔV) of 0.40, and a lethality percentage of 60.30 % (calculated with Formula 2). Similarly, with *Human Coronavirus 229E*, the composite displayed a V_L of 1.46, ΔV

Table 1
Results of compound viricidal tests.

Reference	<i>Feline Calicivirus</i>	<i>Coronavirus 229E</i>
NT pieces after inoculation (0 h)		
Maximum level of detectable viral inactivation	5.68 ± 0.12	5.79 ± 0.13
Value A Log TCID ₅₀	6.18 ± 0.12	6.29 ± 0.13
NT pieces after incubation in darkness		
Maximum level of detectable viral inactivation ^a	5.10 ± 0.13	5.77 ± 0.26
Value B _D Log TCID ₅₀	5.60 ± 0.13	6.27 ± 0.26
NT pieces after UV irradiation		
Maximum level of detectable viral inactivation ^a	5.13 ± 0.13	5.71 ± 0.26
Value B _L Log TCID ₅₀	5.63 ± 0.13	6.21 ± 0.26
T pieces after incubation in darkness		
Maximum level of detectable viral inactivation ^a	4.65 ± 0.08	4.83 ± 0.25
Value C _D Log TCID ₅₀	5.16 ± 0.08	5.33 ± 0.25
T pieces after UV irradiation		
Maximum level of detectable viral inactivation ^a	4.27 ± 0.13	4.30 ± 0.05
Value C _L Log TCID ₅₀	4.77 ± 0.13	4.80 ± 0.05
V_L viricidal activity after UV irradiation	0.86	1.46
V_D of antiviral activity in the dark	0.46	0.94
ΔV antiviral activity of photocatalyst with UV irradiation	0.40	0.52
Case fatality rate (Formula 1)	60.30 %	69.53 %

^a The maximum detectable viral inactivation level is the difference between the viral suspension titer and the cytotoxicity level.

of 0.52 and a lethality percentage of 69.53 %.

Fig. 1-A shows tcid₅₀ titers for each condition, confirming titanium dioxide's viricidal effect, not the polymeric matrix. Low-concentration UV light (0.25 mW/cm²) isn't viricidal or cytotoxic, suggesting virus elimination without cellular damage. All controls and validations meet set standards.

For the PLA/TiO₂ composite, a reduction is observed under dark conditions; however, effectiveness is enhanced with UV irradiation. Some authors, such as Matsuura et al. [12], suggesting that virus inactivation results from changes in morphology, protein degradation, and genome damage induced by the photocatalytic reaction.

In photocatalytic processes (Fig. 2), viral inactivation is attributed to the generation of ROS. The oxidation mechanism involves: (i) excitation on the catalyst surface, generating pairs of electrons and holes (e⁻/h⁺) [17], (ii) e⁻ and h⁺ can rapidly recombine with O₂ and H₂O species adsorbed from the surface, the holes in the valence band react with H₂O producing hydroxyl radicals (•OH), which oxidize the virus chemicals (iii) electrons in the conduction band, after reacting with O₂, produce highly efficient radicals (O₂• and •OOH), initiating reactions that destroy the virus on the surface of the photocatalyst [18].

Fig. 1-B shows that the transmittance of TiO₂ and PLA/TiO₂ composite is higher in the range of 400–900 nm. In the 350–400 nm range, there is a higher absorbance. The bandgap energy, calculated according to Formula 2, is 3.7 eV for TiO₂ and 3.6 eV for PLA/TiO₂, which determines the radiation needed to generate crucial electron-hole pairs in oxidation–reduction processes. The bandgap energy of TiO₂ is a combination of anatase–rutile phases, with a predominance of the anatase phase [19].

Mechanical properties assessed in three printing orientations: vertical, horizontal, and edgewise. Highest Young's modulus: vertical (3977.7 MPa), followed by horizontal (2871.4 MPa) and edgewise (2921.2 MPa). Tensile stress: equal in horizontal and edgewise (53.0 MPa), higher than vertical (45.9 MPa). Vertical elongation at break: 2.5 %, horizontal: 4.7 %, edgewise: 3.3 %. Composite strength comparable to PLA (30–50 MPa) [20], ensuring similar application performance.

In flexural, highest Young's modulus: edgewise (3495.1 MPa), followed by vertical (3363.5 MPa), and horizontal (3081.4 MPa). For flexural stress, edgewise has the highest value (92.3 MPa), followed by horizontal (88.3 MPa), and vertical (67.2 MPa). Elongation at break highest in horizontal (8.1 %), then edgewise (7.0 %), and vertical (2.3 %). Results support previous findings [21], emphasizing the impact of printing orientation on material mechanics.

The SEM images (Fig. 1-c) exhibit presence of a rough texture on the surfaces confirms the absence of layer-to-layer cutting faults. The strong bonding between PLA layers is highlighted, which is essential in 3D printing to ensure uniform distribution of mechanical loads and prevent fractures between layer interfaces.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the composite material maintains its strength within the expected range compared to PLA, suggesting its suitability for similar applications. Optimal adhesion of the layers was evidenced despite the TiO₂ fillers. Additionally, it is established that the range of 300–400 nm is crucial for activating photocatalytic processes of the PLA/TiO₂ composite.

Finally, the antiviral efficacy against both enveloped and non-enveloped viruses is demonstrated. A significant reduction in viral load was observed for viruses such as *Human Coronavirus 229E* by 70 % and *Feline Calicivirus* by 60 % after 4 h of exposure to the treated materials. This antiviral effect is attributed to the generation of ROS during UV irradiation in the bandgap range. This innovation presents an effective and durable solution to mitigate the presence of viruses on plastic surfaces for applications in the additive manufacturing industry and public health protection.

Fig. 1. (a) Results of antiviral assays with *Feline calicivirus* and *Coronavirus*, (b) UV-Vis reflectance spectra of TiO₂ and PLA/TiO₂ and (c) Fractures of pieces under tensile and flexural stresses.

Fig. 2. Photocatalytic inactivation mechanism with antiviral effect.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anyul López-Camacho: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis. **María José Grande:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniel Carazo-Álvarez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **M.Dolores La Rubia:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2024.137039>.

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